

Unrest signals after 46 years of quiescence at Cumbre Vieja, La Palma, Canary Islands

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42 Abstract

43 Monogenetic eruptions are the most common volcanic activity in the world. However, unrest
44 monitoring data are scarce due to the long intervening quiescence periods. This study analyzes
45 unrest signals recorded in one of the largest monogenetic fields in the Canary Islands, Cumbre
46 Vieja (La Palma). Two seismic swarms were registered in October 2017 and February 2018 with
47 b-values of 1.6 ± 0.1 and 2.3 ± 0.2 respectively suggesting an intense magmatic fluids
48 contribution, gas and/or magma. Both swarms were linked to changes in gas emissions.
49 Increases in hydrogen concentration, and $(R/R_a)_c$ up to 7.52 ± 0.05 , were recorded before the
50 first swarm, at the sampling point closest to where seismicity was located, indicating a deep gas
51 input. After the second swarm, increases in $(R/R_a)_c$ and thoron soil concentration were recorded
52 at two locations. This dataset is compatible with a stalled magmatic intrusion at ca 25 km depth,
53 with an estimated volume between $5.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$ and $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$.

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57 Keywords: Monogenetic volcanic field, Magmatic intrusion, Seismic swarms, Helium and
58 carbon isotopes, Radon and thoron concentrations in soil, La Palma.

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63 1. Introduction

64 Volcanic eruptions are usually preceded by increases in background seismicity and gaseous
65 emissions (Aiuppa et al., 2007; C. López et al., 2012; White & McCausland, 2016; Lee et al.,
66 2018). Ground deformation is also typically recorded (C. López et al., 2012; Lamolda et al.,
67 2017; Stephens et al., 2017). Changes in gravity (Sainz-Maza Aparicio et al., 2014),
68 geomagnetic (Kanda et al., 2010) and geoelectric fields (Zlotnicki, 2015; Wawrzyniak et al.,
69 2017) are also measured. These variations are cataloged as precursory signals of eruptions,
70 allowing volcanologists to forecast where and when an eruption could occur (Boué et al., 2015;
71 National Academies of Sciences & Medicine, 2017). However, in some cases the precursory
72 activity ends in a failed eruption (Moran et al., 2011; Falsaperla et al., 2014). This situation is
73 particularly common in monogenetic fields (Cruz-Reyna & Yokoyama, 2011; Albert et al., 2016).

74

75 Monogenetic volcanic fields are wide areas where volcanism has taken place over millions of
76 years as single eruptive episodes (Phillipson et al., 2013). This kind of volcanism is the most
77 widespread type of volcanic activity in the world, mainly expressed as mafic eruptions with a low
78 explosive eruption index (Phillipson et al., 2013; Martí et al., 2016). Due to its long quiescence
79 periods and unexpected eruption locations, there is a huge lack of monitoring data (Albert et al.,
80 2016).

81

82 Monogenetic volcanoes have been traditionally related to single batches of magma (Hasenaka
83 & Carmichael, 1985; Pérez-López et al., 2011) but recent studies show that a single eruption
84 may display geochemical changes that require multiple magma batches (Needham et al., 2011;
85 Albert et al., 2015). Failed eruptions (stalled magma batches) in monogenetic fields may

86 constitute the opening path for future eruptions. Therefore, volcanic hazard assessment will be
87 improved by combining the geochemical, geophysical and petrological data to understand the
88 dynamics of the plumbing system (Klügel et al., 1997, 2000, 2005; C. López et al., 2012; Martí
89 et al., 2016).

90
91 In this study, the unrest signals recorded at Cumbre Vieja are reported and analyzed. Two
92 seismic swarms were detected in October 2017 and February 2018. Both were preceded and
93 accompanied by changes in helium and carbon dioxide emissions, but no ground deformation
94 was measured. After the second swarm, increases in thoron concentration in soil were recorded
95 at two sites located along the Cumbre Vieja rift. The most plausible interpretation of these
96 results is a magmatic intrusion from depth and/or an active reservoir beneath that rift.

97 98 99 2. Geological context

100 The Canary Islands are a 500 km east-west chain of seven major volcanic islands and a
101 number of smaller islets. Subaerial volcanic activity in the archipelago began around 20 Ma ago
102 building the eastern islands, Lanzarote and Fuerteventura. A Jurassic oceanic crust is present
103 underneath the islands as indicated by gabbro xenoliths in tholeiitic mid-ocean ridge basalt
104 (MORB) (Schmincke et al., 1998).

105
106 La Palma is the north-westernmost, fifth-largest (706 km²) and second-highest (2430 masl) of
107 the Canary Islands (Fig 1). The geology of La Palma can be divided into three major units
108 (Hausen, 1969). The first is formed by the older basal complex (c.a 4.0 to 3.0 Ma), which
109 includes a Pliocene seamount and a plutonic complex (Staudigel & Schmincke, 1984). The
110 second is the older volcanic series (1.8 to 0.5 Ma) including Garafía volcano, Taburiente shield
111 volcano, Bejenado edifice and Cumbre Nueva. The last geological unit (125 ka to present) is
112 Cumbre Vieja, located at the southern part of the island.

113
114 Subaerial volcanic activity at La Palma started 1.8 Ma ago on the northern side of the island
115 building Garafía volcano, which partly collapsed 1.2 Ma ago toward the southwest (Ancochea et
116 al., 1994). The depression thus formed was filled by intense volcanism, resulting in Taburiente
117 volcano, an edifice 25 km in diameter and approximately 3000 m in height (Troll & Carracedo,
118 2016). Its eruptions were mainly felsic, indicating magmatic evolution from basaltic to more
119 differentiated magmas (Troll & Carracedo, 2016).

120
121 The volcanic activity migrated southward during the advanced stages of Taburiente, culminating
122 in Cumbre Nueva. This volcano underwent a giant landslide on its western flank 560 ka ago
123 (Carracedo et al., 2001). The resulting depression, Valle de Aridane, led to the growth of
124 Taburiente caldera (Fig. 1a), a spectacular eroded structure exposing part of the submarine
125 edifice (Ancochea et al., 1994). Bejenado volcano then arose through the landslide deposits,
126 and after a quiescent period, volcanic activity migrated southward 123 ka ago, building Cumbre
127 Vieja.

128
129 At Cumbre Vieja, the most active basaltic volcanic field in the Canaries (Troll & Carracedo,

130 2016), vents are mainly located in a 20 km north-south rift reaching up to 1950 masl. All
131 historical eruptions and their lava flows on La Palma have occurred in this volcanic field
132 (Romero Ruiz, 1989), the last two being San Juan (1949) and Teneguía (1971) (Fig. 1a). San
133 Juan involved three eruptive centers (Llano del Banco, El Duraznero and Hoyo Negro, Fig. 1a)
134 and seismicity was felt even years before the eruption (Rubio, 1950). Petrological studies
135 revealed the occurrence of three magma mixing events matching the timescales of the unrest
136 activity (Albert et al., 2016). This eruption may have developed a normal fault system on the
137 western flank of Cumbre Vieja (Fig. 1a). Some authors consider this structure a first sign of
138 instability of the western flank of the monogenetic field (S. J. Day et al., 1999; Ward & Day,
139 2001), however a recent study by González et al. [2010] links that system with a flank
140 stabilization.

141
142 Seismicity was felt from months to weeks before the onset of Teneguía eruption (Klügel et al.,
143 1997) and there was one fatality due to gas emissions. The estimated erupted volume was
144 $4.3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$ (López Acevedo et al., 2014). Barker et al. [2015] reported magma storing depths
145 comparable to those of the San Juan event, which showed deeper crystallization than early
146 Cumbre Vieja events.

147
148 There is only one visible gas emanation point at La Palma. It is located inside Taburiente
149 caldera (Dos Aguas, QP60 in Fig. 1b) and is a CO₂-rich bubbling cold spring with the highest
150 $(R/R_a)_c$ values reported for thermal fluids in the entire Canary Islands ranging between $9.42 \pm$
151 0.08 to 10.24 ± 0.07 (Pérez, 1994; Hilton et al., 2000; Padrón et al., 2012, 2015). Since those
152 values are clearly above the MORB range (Graham, 2002), some authors have suggested a
153 small but persistent component of plume-type helium (J. M. D. Day & Hilton, 2011; Padrón et al.,
154 2015) in accordance with the hot-spot model proposed for the origin of Canary Islands
155 (Carracedo et al., 1998).

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158 **Fig. 1.** Location of La Palma. a) Simplified geological map. Caldera de Taburiente rim, Cumbre Nueva and Cumbre
 159 Vieja rift (Troll & Carracedo, 2016) , the 1949 fault system (IGME, 2010) and the last two historical eruptions are
 160 highlighted (Troll & Carracedo, 2016). b) The IGN volcanic monitoring network and the two AEMET (Agencia Estatal
 161 de Meteorología, 2019) meteorological stations, PASO and FUEN.

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3. Monitoring network and methodology

165 The volcanic monitoring network deployed on La Palma by the Instituto Geográfico Nacional
 166 (IGN, 2019a) (hereinafter IGN) is shown in Fig. 1b. It is described here alongside the
 167 methodology employed in this work.

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3.1. Seismology

170 Prior to October 2017, the seismic monitoring network consisted of the stations TBT, EHIG,
 171 CPUN, CJED and CTEN. In the first fortnight of October 2017, CVIE, CENR, CROM, CGOR,
 172 CMIR, CLLA and CFLP were added (yellow triangles in Fig. 1b). All had 3C broadband
 173 seismometers except CVIE, which had a short-period sensor. Sampling frequency was 100 Hz
 174 and data were transmitted in real-time to the IGN's network, *Red Sísmica Nacional* (hereinafter
 175 RSN). Earthquake locations and local magnitudes were determined using a 3-layer velocity

176 model based on Dañoibeitia [1985]. Both P- and S-wave arrivals were manually picked for better
177 constraint of focal depths. The seismic dataset used in this work was obtained from the
178 Canarian earthquake catalog (IGN, 2019b) which is available online in real-time.
179 Besides the event histogram, seismic energy release estimation (Gutenberg & Richter, 1956),
180 and difference in arrival time between P and S phases, two more analyses were made. First, in
181 order to improve location of events and trying to find possible event alignments and/or pattern, a
182 relative relocation process using hypoDD software was applied (Waldhauser & Ellsworth, 2000).
183 The only times employed were for phases P, weighted 1; and S, weighted 0.2 for the October
184 2017 swarm and 0.5 for February 2018 seismicity, were employed. Maximum distances
185 between hypocenters of 4 km were chosen, and the condition number (Waldhauser, 2001)
186 always remained between 40-80. Relocation errors were estimated with a 90% confidence level,
187 relocating a random subset of the original events (Schultz et al., 2014). The second analysis
188 was the determination of b-value and completeness magnitude (hereinafter M_c). The b-value is
189 a constant that characterizes every frequency-magnitude distribution (FMD) of the earthquake
190 catalog (B. Gutenberg & Richter, 1944) reflecting the ratio between the number of large and
191 small magnitude earthquakes. A global average b-value for complete catalogs is around 1
192 (Bridges & Gao, 2006). However, in highly fractured rock it shows higher values, and, in some
193 volcanic regions, even reaches values higher than 3. This parameter has been used to identify
194 active magma batches, and to study the spatial and temporal evolution of seismicity during
195 unrest processes (Stephen R. McNutt, 2005; Ibáñez et al., 2012; Carmen López et al., 2017).
196 The b-values were determined employing three different methods: least squares,
197 maximum-likelihood (Aki, 1965), and bootstrap (using the maximum-likelihood method as
198 estimator) with 1000 resamplings (Efron, 1982). The error estimation for each method was
199 calculated as follows: i) for least squares the b-value error was obtained from the linear
200 regression standard error, ii) for maximum-likelihood the improved uncertainty equation from
201 Shi and Bold [1982] and Marzocchi and Sandri [2003] was employed and, iii) for bootstrap the
202 estimated error was determined by the standard error of the mean of the 1000 resamplings. The
203 maximum number of events per magnitude method was applied to determine M_c , except for
204 bootstrap where its value was the mean of all iterations. Though all methods are sensitive to the
205 choice of M_c , in its estimation, the maximum curvature method proved to be very stable to
206 sample size (Zhou et al., 2018).

207 208 3.2. Geochemistry

209 The geochemical monitoring network included free and dissolved gas sampling points (blue
210 circles in Fig. 1b) sampled since the beginning of 2016, and two continuous stations for
211 monitoring radon and thoron concentrations in soil (green circles in Fig. 1b).

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213 Sampling point QP60, named Dos Aguas, is a CO₂-rich bubbling cold spring. Gas samples were
214 collected every two-three months employing a submerged funnel. Using a syringe, gas flow was
215 forced to pass through a lead-glass bottle where the sample was stored. In contrast, QP63 is a
216 small well (2 meters in depth, down to water level, and 70 cm in diameter approximately)
217 located around 150 meters from the sea. Even though its water level follows sea tides, its
218 electrical conductivity (10 - 15 mS/cm) is clearly below the mean Atlantic Ocean value (50-57
219 mS/cm) (Friedman et al., 2017), and suggests a mix between sea and fresh water. Dissolved

220 gas samples were taken every two-three months using the method described by Capasso and
221 Inguaggiato [1998]. Gas analyses, total composition and carbon and helium isotopic ratios were
222 carried out at INGV laboratories in Palermo, Italy, following the methodology described by
223 Paonita et al. [2012]. In order to study a possible contribution of the crustal radiogenic helium
224 ($^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$), which could explain decreases and/or variations in air-corrected helium isotopic ratios
225 (Sano et al., 2015), $(R/R_a)_c$, the procedure described by Ballentine et al. [2012] was followed.

226
227 The stations QP40 and QP41 continuously recorded radon (^{222}Rn) and thoron (^{220}Rn)
228 concentrations in soil by means of SARAD RTM2200, with sampling periods of 60 min. Both
229 were installed in October 2017. Cylindrical PVC tubes, 70 cm long, 16 cm in diameter and
230 sealed at the top, were buried 70 cm deep. Soil gas was pumped continuously (0.3 L/min) from
231 the tubes to the SARAD monitors through a pneumatic closed circuit. A water trap was placed
232 before the gas inlet of the instrument. Both stations also recorded barometric pressure, air
233 temperature and relative humidity inside the closed circuit. In order to remove most of the
234 dependence on atmospheric parameters, 12-h and 24-h contributions (Fig. 1 in supplementary
235 material), zero-phase Butterworth low pass filters (Smith, 2007) were applied to radon and
236 thoron concentration records.

237 238 3.3. Geodesy

239 The initial GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) network consisted of five dual frequency
240 receivers: LPAL, LP01, LP02, LP03 and MAZO (red squares in Fig. 1b). All belonged to IGN
241 except MAZO (GRAFCAN, 2019). During October 2017, station LP04 was deployed close to
242 the area where seismicity was located. Data were transmitted in real-time to quantify daily
243 surface deformation and three-dimensional displacements.

244
245 Daily coordinates were obtained using Bernese v5.2 (Dach et al., 2015), applying
246 ocean-loading model FES2004 (Lyard et al., 2006) and the IGS (International GNSS Service)
247 absolute antenna phase center models. Precise satellite IGS orbits were also considered. Plate
248 movement was removed using the Nuvel-1A model (DeMets et al., 1994) and coordinates were
249 determined using the ITRF2014 reference frame (Altamimi et al., 2016).

250 251 252 4. Results

253 In the following subsections, the geophysical and geochemical data acquired by the different
254 sub networks are analyzed.

255 256 4.1. Seismic dataset

257 258 4.1.1. Previous seismicity

259 Until May 2017, IGN had deployed two seismic stations on La Palma, TBT from November 1,
260 1974 to July 23, 2010 first with a short period sensor and later with a broadband sensor, and
261 EHIG (since January 15, 2002). These seismic stations located seven events between August 1,
262 2005 and October 1, 2017 (IGN, 2019b). Although the number of seismic stations was too low,
263 swarms such as those described in this work would have been detected if they had occurred.

4.1.2. First swarm

In the first fortnight of October 2017, at least 128 earthquakes were recorded and located by the RSN (Fig. 2a and Table 1). This seismic series was divided into two: from October 7 to 9 and, from October 13 to 14 (Fig. 2b) the maximum number of events was recorded on October 8, 46 % of the total number. Mean hypocentral depth obtained from the seismic catalog was 21.2 ± 2.9 km.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the two swarms

Swarm	Depth (km)	Magnitude (mbLg)	ΔE ($\cdot 10^9$ J)	Estimated intruded volume ($\cdot 10^{-5}$ km ³)	Mc (mbLg)	b-value	ΔT_{sTP} (s)	Number of events	
October 2017	Max	33	2.7 ± 0.1	2.88	1.9	1.4 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	CJED: 2.75	
	Mean	21	1.5 ± 0.1					CENR: 2.62	
	Min	12	0.9 ± 0.1					EHIG: 2.54	
February 2018	Max	33	2.6 ± 0.1	6.68	1.9 ± 0.1	2.3 ± 0.2	CJED: 3.18	84	
	Mean	26	2.0 ± 0.1						CENR: 3.17
	Min	22	1.4 ± 0.1						EHIG: 3.04

The relocated events for this swarm are shown in Fig. 3a with blue dots, while the initial event locations are plotted with white dots. From the 124 original events, 116 were successfully relocated, covering a large area and showing no spatial alignment but with a location predominantly westward from the Cumbre Vieja rift axis. Relocation errors are lower in depth than in the horizontal plane (Fig. 3a). The 90 % confidence level ellipse plane shows a NE-SW direction in the horizontal plane, probably due to the seismic network geometry during this swarm.

Magnitudes ranged from 0.9 to 2.7 mbLg, the estimation of the total seismic energy released in this period being $2.88 \cdot 10^9$ J, of which 78 % was released from October 7 to 9 (Fig. 2b).

The Mc result was very stable for this swarm, 1.4 mbLg, but that was not the case for the b-value (top panel Fig. 2e and Table 1), probably due to the low number of events recorded (Nava et al., 2017) and the method employed (Section 3.1). The estimated error for maximum-likelihood method matches the estimation error for a 100 events sample determined by Bender [1983], $0.1 \cdot b$ -value. The bootstrap result is in good agreement with the error range, 10% error, found by Bengoubou-Valérius and Gilbert [2013] for a low sample size. Even so, in order to obtain a result closer to the real b-value characteristic of this swarm, the mean and its standard error 1.6 ± 0.1 were selected. This procedure was followed for the second swarm as well.

Fig. 2. Seismic data. a) Histogram of events from April 2017 to September 2018. Swarms on October 2017 (blue) and February 2018 (red) are highlighted. b) and c) Detailed histogram of the two swarms along with accumulated seismic energy released (green line). d) Time difference between P- and S- for each event in each swarm at the closest stations. e) Estimation of the M_c and b -value for each swarm

4.1.3. Second swarm

From February 11 to 15, 2018, a total of 84 events were recorded (Fig. 2c), a lower number than during the first swarm. Their magnitude ranged from 1.4 to 2.6 mbLg, and the estimated seismic energy released was $6.68 \cdot 10^9$ J, twice that of the first swarm. It is important to note that on February 14, 69 % of the earthquakes were recorded, corresponding to 53 % of the total energy released.

For this swarm, the b -value error is higher for the maximum-likelihood method than in the first. This is obviously due to the lower number of events with respect to the first swarm (Bender, 1983). Nevertheless, least squares and bootstrap show similar error values to the previous swarm. Following the same procedure, the mean and its standard error were determined in order to find a value closer to the real b -value, 2.3 ± 0.2 (bottom panel Fig. 2e and Table 1). The M_c was 1.9 ± 0.1 mbLg. Both results were higher than for the first swarm.

The mean depth obtained from the catalog was 26.4 ± 2.3 km, deeper than for the first swarm. This result is compatible with time differences between P- and S-phase, $\Delta T_{S T_P}$ (Fig. 2d). The October events showed a lower mean value for $\Delta T_{S T_P}$ at all stations than February events (Table 1). Relocation considering both swarms simultaneously also confirms the depth difference (Fig. 3c).

In Fig. 3b, the relocated events for this swarm are shown with red dots while unrelocated event locations are plotted with white dots. From the 84 initial events, 80 were successfully relocated. In contrast to the relocation result for the first swarm (blue dots Fig. 3a), for the second swarm

326 both unrelocated and relocated events were mainly located below the Cumbre Vieja rift and its
 327 eastern flank. In this case, the relocated events seem to be grouped below the rift, at least a
 328 considerable number of them. The 90 % confidence level ellipse shows an E-W direction.

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 330 By comparing the relocated events of both swarms (Figs. 3a and 3b), it seems that there was a
 331 slight eastward migration of seismicity. To confirm this, both series were relocated together (Fig.
 332 3c). Since hypoDD software retrieves a relative relocation and both series were considered, it
 333 was possible to assert that the first swarm was located to the west of the second.

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 337 **Fig. 3.** Relocation using hypoDD software. In panels a) and b), white circles represent original locations while blue
 338 (October 2017) and red (February 2018) are the relocated events. For the first swarm, the main relocation
 339 parameters were: WTCTP=1, WTCTS=0.2, WRCT=0.3, WDCT=4, DAMP=25 and CND=47-70, while for the second
 340 they were: WTCTP=1, WTCTS=0.2, WRCT=0.2, WDCT=4, DAMP=20 and CND=52-78. Panel c) shows the
 341 relocation (blue circles for the first swarm and red for the second) considering both seismic series together with the
 342 following parameters: WTCTP=1, WTCTS=0.5, WRCT=0.4, WDCT=4, DAMP=35 and CND=46-67. In the right lower
 343 corner of each figure, an estimation of relocation error is shown, 90% confidence ellipse, ground plan (top) and depth
 344 (bottom). Acronyms stand for: WTCTP and WTCTS, weight for catalog P- and S-wave respectively; WRCT, cutoff
 345 threshold for outliers located on the tails of the catalog data; WDCT, maximum event separation distance [km] for
 346 catalog data; DAMP, damping factor; and CND, condition number for the system of double-difference equations.

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349 4.2. Geochemical dataset

350 Before October 2017, the air-corrected helium isotope ratio (Sakamoto et al., 1992), $(R/R_a)_c$
 351 showed a slight decrease at QP60 from a maximum value of 9.95 ± 0.07 on September 2016 to
 352 9.16 ± 0.07 , one year afterwards (black dashed line Fig. 4a). In contrast, $(R/R_a)_c$ increased
 353 slightly at QP63, reaching 7.23 ± 0.05 on September 2017 (gray dashed line Fig. 4a). After the
 354 first swarm, $(R/R_a)_c$ at QP60 showed a higher variation than before, between 9.76 ± 0.07 and
 355 8.76 ± 0.08 (the lowest value in the entire dataset). Whereas at QP63, $(R/R_a)_c$ reached the two
 356 highest values in the whole record, 7.94 ± 0.05 after the first swarm and 8.23 ± 0.12 after the
 357 second, afterwards were dropping to values below 7. During 2018 and the beginning of 2019,
 358 QP60 and QP63 presented similar trends (Fig. 4a).

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In Fig. 5a, R/R_a ratios were plotted against $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ for both sampling points, QP60 and QP63. Due to the different sampling features, the mixing lines begin at two different points. Since at QP60 free gases were sampled, the start point is the relation for air: $R/R_a = 1$ and $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne} = 0.318$, whereas at QP63 dissolved gas samples were taken, the initial point is the Air Saturated Water point (ASW): $R/R_a = 1$, $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne} = 0.285$. Two different end-members were used since QP60 samples were clearly above the Mid-Ocean Rift Basalts (MORB) level, $8 \pm 1 R_a$ (Graham, 2002), due to a slight plume-type helium contribution (Padrón et al., 2015). In contrast, QP63 samples fitted well with a standard MORB value.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the isotopic ratios and gas concentrations at sampling points QP60 and QP63

Sampling Point		$\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$ (‰)	$(R/R_a)_c$	$^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$	CO_2 (%)	H_2 (ppm)	Samples
QP60	Max	-3.4 ± 0.1	9.95 ± 0.07	160.7	99.2 ± 3.0	2.7 ± 0.1	13
	Mean	-3.6 ± 0.1	9.58 ± 0.09	82.2	98.0 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	
	Min	-3.7 ± 0.1	8.76 ± 0.08	25.7	97.0 ± 3.0	1.0 ± 0.1	
QP63	Max	-7.1 ± 0.1	8.23 ± 0.12	2.75	56.6 ± 3.0	50.8 ± 2.5	15
	Mean	-8.3 ± 0.2	7.07 ± 0.15	1.43	14.7 ± 3.3	9.4 ± 3.8	
	Min	-10.3 ± 0.1	6.10 ± 0.06	0.44	3.8 ± 3.0	1.0 ± 0.1	

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In Fig. 4b, an estimation of crustal radiogenic helium ($^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$) is shown. The highest variations were those of QP60 samples, reaching 1.3 ppm after the second swarm. At QP63 the $^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$ contribution was lower than at QP60, only noteworthy in March 2017.

The isotopic carbon dioxide composition, $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$, is shown in Fig. 4c. At QP60 it ranged from -3.4 ‰ to -3.7 ‰ exhibiting stability even during the swarm periods (Fig. 4c and Fig. 5b). In contrast, at QP63 there was an increase during 2017, reaching its maximum value on June 20 2017, -7.1 ‰. During the swarm periods, $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$ in QP63 ranged between -8.5 ‰ and -8.2 ‰, afterwards rising up to -7.3 ‰ on June 6 2018 and later decreasing constantly to -10.3 ‰ (Fig. 4c).

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Fig. 4. Dataset from sampling points QP60 (squares) and QP63 (circles). From top to bottom: a) air-corrected helium isotope ratio $(R/R_a)_c$ and MORB range (Graham, 2002), b) crustal ^4He contribution, $^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$, c) $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$ vs. VPDB and MORB range (Pineau & Javoy, 1983), d) carbon dioxide concentration, $[\text{CO}_2]$, and e) hydrogen concentration, $[\text{H}_2]$. In each plot, both swarm periods are highlighted as vertical bars, October 2017 in blue and February 2018 in red.

At QP60, CO_2 concentration (Fig. 4d) remained stable close to the saturation value, between $97 \pm 3 \%$ and $99 \pm 3 \%$. Instead, the sampling point QP63 showed lower concentrations, fluctuating between $5.4 \pm 3 \%$ and $23.3 \pm 3 \%$ before October 2017. After the first swarm, CO_2 reached its maximum of $56.6 \pm 3 \%$ at QP63, 2.4 times higher than before. During 2018, CO_2 remained consistently below 20 % at QP63. Plotting CO_2 concentration against $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CO}_2$ (Fig. 5b) for both sampling points shows the great difference between QP60 and QP63.

Hydrogen concentrations recorded at QP60 and QP63 are shown in Fig. 4e. Since the detection limit for H_2 was 1 ppm, values at QP60 remained lower than or close to this limit during practically the entire record. In contrast, in January 2017 hydrogen concentration reached a value of 15 ± 0.8 ppm at QP63, and the maximum was recorded before the first swarm, 50.8 ± 2.5 ppm. Before and after the second swarm, 20.5 ± 1.0 ppm and 31.8 ± 1.6 ppm were recorded respectively. During the summer of 2018 there was also a clear increase in $[\text{H}_2]$ reaching 11.7 ± 0.6 ppm on August 8, 2018.

408
 409 **Fig. 5.** a) Air helium isotope ratio, R/R_a , vs. $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$. Two mixing lines were considered since the sampling points
 410 QP60 and QP63 had different features, free and dissolved gas respectively. Two mantle end-members (maximum
 411 values recorded at each point) were used, 10.04 ± 0.07 for QP60 reported by Padrón et al. [2015] on September 29,
 412 2012, and $8 \pm 1 R_a$, mean MORB value (Graham, 2002), for QP63 measurements, which might be justified by
 413 different magma reservoirs being involved. ASW and Air stands for Air Saturated Water ($R/R_a=1$, $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}=0.285$)
 414 and Air ($R/R_a = 1$ and $\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}=0.318$). b) Carbon dioxide concentration vs. $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ with the MORB range
 415 highlighted (Pineau & Javoy, 1983). In both panels samples from QP60 and QP63 are shown by squares and circles
 416 respectively.
 417
 418

419 During October 2017, the mean radon concentration at QP40 was $333 \pm 160 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ (Fig. 6a4).
 420 After a data gap (power supply problems), radon showed higher values ($599 \pm 160 \text{ Bq/m}^3$) until
 421 July 2018. There was a decrease from July to October 2018, fluctuating around 427 ± 209
 422 Bq/m^3 . Afterwards, radon returned to slightly higher values, $741 \pm 168 \text{ Bq/m}^3$.
 423

424 At QP41, radon increased constantly from the beginning, reaching a maximum of 1185 ± 53
 425 Bq/m^3 at the end of February 2018 (Fig. 6b4). After another data gap (system failure) in June
 426 2018, radon showed abrupt variations and then remained at low values until October 2018.
 427 Afterwards, radon increased continuously up to $1440 \pm 59 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ on November 16, 2018, and
 428 then dropped to background levels in early December 2018. From that date on, radon showed a
 429 constant increase until the end of 2018, and later it remained fluctuating around a mean of 660
 430 $\pm 247 \text{ Bq/m}^3$.
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Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the parameters recorded at both continuous radon/thoron stations

Station	Radon (Bq/m ³)	Thoron (Bq/m ³)	Atmospheric Pressure (mb)	Air Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Number of Measurements
QP40	Max	1,348 ± 57	404 ± 31	931.5 ± 4.7	46.2 ± 0.5	98.7 ± 1.9
	Mean	581 ± 37	25 ± 8	920.3 ± 4.6	21.4 ± 0.5	72.5 ± 1.5
	Min	5 ± 3	0	899.1 ± 4.5	6.5 ± 0.5	32.4 ± 0.7
QP41	Max	1,440 ± 59	105 ± 15	976.9 ± 4.9	49.8 ± 0.5	99.2 ± 1.9
	Mean	309 ± 27	19 ± 7	965.4 ± 4.8	22.9 ± 0.5	74.1 ± 1.5
	Min	0	0	944.6 ± 4.7	11.7 ± 0.5	39.9 ± 0.8

439

440

441 Thoron remained stable at QP40 from October 2017 until the beginning of February 2018 with a
 442 mean value of 9 ± 3 Bq/m³ (Fig. 6a5). A higher mean of 23 ± 5 Bq/m³ was recorded until late
 443 July, after replacing the equipment due to pump failure in February 2018. A clear leap in thoron
 444 concentration was thus recorded. From August until early October 2018, thoron concentration
 445 rose and remained around 39 ± 10 Bq/m³, and then decreased to previous levels, 27 ± 6 Bq/m³.

446

447 Thoron at QP41 remained stable (Fig. 6b5) around 15 ± 4 Bq/m³ from the beginning of the
 448 series until April 2018, with the exception of a sharp increase in mid-December 2017, reaching
 449 34 ± 7 Bq/m³, coincident with a radon decrease (Fig. 6b4). During June and July 2018, thoron
 450 showed higher levels (26 ± 6 Bq/m³) until August, when it dropped to previous values.
 451 Afterwards, thoron exhibited a slight growth trend from a mean value of 16 ± 4 Bq/m³ to 22 ± 4
 452 Bq/m³ in February 2019. In order to test this, a linear regression of the filtered thoron
 453 concentration signal was carried out. Its result, plotted in Fig. 6b5 as a dashed black line, shows
 454 a low but positive slope.

455

456

457

458 **Fig. 6.** Records at QP40 (a) and QP41 (b): relative humidity (a1 and b1), atmospheric temperature (a2 and b2),
 459 barometric pressure and normalized accumulated rainfall (black line) (a3 and b3), soil radon concentration (a4 and
 460 b4), soil thoron concentration (a5 and b5) and radon-thoron ratio (a6 and b6). Atmospheric temperature and rainfall
 461 was obtained from AEMET stations PASO for QP40 and FUEN for QP41 (Magenta diamonds in Fig. 1). All records
 462 were filtered by a Butterworth low-pass filter and plotted over raw data (green lines). Both swarm periods and main
 463 failures are highlighted as vertical bars

464
465

466 **4.3. GNSS dataset**

467 In Fig. 7, GNSS centered data from stations that were operative during both seismic swarms
 468 (LPAL, LP01, LP02, LP03 and MAZO) are plotted, covering from mid April 2017 to June 2018.
 469 Deformation components showed random variations below centimeter values. Due to its
 470 intrinsic lower accuracy, fluctuations in the up component were clearer (Santerre, 1991).

471

472 Throughout the whole analyzed period there was no surface deformation attributable to volcanic
 473 activity or seismic swarms. There were short time periods when the deformation signal
 474 underwent abrupt changes, but it always returned to previous values. No permanent
 475 displacement was recorded.

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479 **Fig. 7.** Records at GNSS stations from mid April 2017 to June 2018. Each panel shows daily components in cm.
 480 North, East and Up components are in purple, blue and green respectively. Seismic swarm periods are highlighted in
 481 blue for October 2017 and red for February 2018

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484 The fact that surface deformation was not observed does not dismiss the possibility of a

485 magmatic intrusion. In order to estimate the maximum magma volume that could have intruded
 486 with no ground deformation detected by the GNSS network, a point magma source situated in
 487 the seismicity area at 25 km deep was simulated between the swarms (Fig. 8). The Mogi model
 488 (Mogi, 1958) shows that a volume of $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$ would produce a permanent deformation of
 489 around 1 cm at the GNSS stations near the swarms: LP01, LP03, LP04 and MAZO (Table in Fig.
 490 8).

491
 492 The Mogi model was chosen since an estimated maximum magma volume was required.
 493 Furthermore, the direct problem had to be computed because in fact there were no deformation
 494 data for inversion. Moreover, the number of parameters of any model must be as low as
 495 possible since otherwise they would be the result of arbitrary assumptions. For these reasons,
 496 the Mogi model was the most suitable.

497
 498 To sum up, it is possible that an intruded magma volume up to $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$ at 25 km deep could
 499 produce deformations below the 1 cm detection threshold of the GNSS network. Any larger
 500 intrusion would have been detected.

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503
 504 **Fig. 8.** Estimation of displacements in each component at each GNSS station assuming a Mogi model located at 25
 505 km deep (not to scale) with a source of $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$ total volume. The two swarms are shown with blue dots for
 506 October 2017 and red for February 2018

507

508

509 5. Discussion

510

511 During 2016 and until September 2017, $(R/R_a)_c$ at QP60 showed a constant decrease (black
512 dashed line in Fig. 4a) from values between 9.63 ± 0.08 and 9.95 ± 0.07 , in the range of
513 previously reported values (Hilton et al., 2000; Padrón et al., 2015), to 9.16 ± 0.07 . A high
514 contribution of plume-derived helium relative to MORB-type typified QP60 (Padrón et al., 2015).
515 This fact is reflected in R/R_a data at QP60 since they were clearly above the standard MORB
516 value (Fig. 5a). Furthermore, their $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ values (Fig. 4c) were similar to those reported for
517 Teide fumaroles (Melián et al., 2012), pointing to an endogenous origin (Pineau & Javoy, 1983)
518 (Fig. 5b). Under these conditions, the maximum $(R/R_a)_c$ ever measured at QP60, 10.24 ± 0.07
519 (Padrón et al., 2015), can be considered as an end-member (Padrón et al., 2012). Therefore,
520 the decrease recorded in $(R/R_a)_c$ at QP60 could be related to an increase in crustal helium,
521 ${}^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$, contribution (Tedesco, 1997; Capasso et al., 2005b; Padrón et al., 2013) as suggested
522 by its estimation following the procedure described in Ballentine et al. [2002] (Fig. 4b). This
523 extra ${}^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$ input could be linked to microfracturing due to the tectonic stress, releasing part of
524 the radiogenic helium accumulated in the uppermost mantle and/or crust after uranium and
525 thorium decay (Moreira et al., 2003; Lowenstern et al., 2014).

526

527 Instead, $(R/R_a)_c$ exhibited a slight increase at QP63 prior to October 2017 (gray dashed line in
528 Fig. 4a) reaching 7.23 ± 0.05 on September 19, 2017. This growth was probably related to a
529 ${}^3\text{He}$ -rich magmatic gas input, as several authors have reported for other volcanic areas
530 (Carapezza et al., 2004; Capasso et al., 2005b; Padrón et al., 2013; Sano et al., 2015). This ${}^3\text{He}$
531 contribution seems to be related to a MORB end-member, $8 \pm 1 R_a$ (Graham, 2002), as
532 suggested by the mixing curve for QP63 in Fig. 5a. This deep helium contribution was
533 accompanied by $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ values measured at QP63, close to the MORB range (Pineau &
534 Javoy, 1983) (Fig. 4c) and matching the highest values reported for this isotopic ratio in soil
535 gases on La Palma (Padrón et al., 2015) with the exception of QP60. Together, these data
536 suggest that this sampling point provides a preferential vent for deep magmatic gases (Capasso
537 et al., 2005; Padrón et al., 2012). As a result, QP63 showed an anomalous carbon dioxide
538 concentration, visibly higher than the standard sea surface value (Sweeney et al., 2016).

539

540 Regarding the increase in $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ at QP63 prior to October 2017, reaching $-7.1 \pm 0.1 \text{‰}$ on
541 June 20 2017, it is important to note that in 2018 there was another growth during the same
542 period (summer), suggesting a seasonal pattern. Taking in to account the small amount of algae
543 present at this sampling point, CO_2 isotopic fractionation could take place during photosynthesis
544 process (Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow, 2001), which is higher during summer, and hence, both slight
545 increases in $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ may have been due to this fact.

546

547 Another anomalous gaseous emission at QP63 was detected in the hydrogen concentration,
548 $[\text{H}_2]$, prior to October 2017. On February 17 2017 and on September 19, 2017, 16 days before
549 the first swarm, $[\text{H}_2]$ reached 15.0 ± 0.8 and 50.8 ± 2.5 ppm respectively, compared to a base
550 level for $[\text{H}_2]$ in air of 0.5 ppm (Derwent et al., 2019). These increases could be related to
551 stress-induced microfracturing (Ito et al., 1999; Saruwatari et al., 2004) prior to the first swarm in

552 October 2017. However, a biological origin is not unlikely since QP63 is a very small well close
553 to the sea with a small amount of algae present (Das & Veziroğlu, 2001). Since there was no
554 seasonal trend in $[H_2]$ at QP63 related to algal photosynthesis (Kirk, 1994) the first hypothesis
555 seems more plausible. Another fact that supports the stress-induced microfracturing
556 explanation is the good correlation between $[H_2]$ at QP63 and estimated $^4He_{crust}$ at QP60, even
557 when the sampling dates do not match exactly. Both gaseous species have been related with
558 rock stress and microfracturing (Tedesco, 1997; Ito et al., 1999; Saruwatari et al., 2004; G.
559 Capasso, Carapezza, et al., 2005; Padrón et al., 2013), and in the recorded dataset each
560 increase in hydrogen concentration matches rises in crustal helium (Figs. 4b and 4e).

561

562 As mentioned, in October 2017 at least 128 earthquakes were detected and located (Table 1).
563 Three different methods for b-value estimation reported results higher than one (top panel in Fig.
564 2e). It is noteworthy that two of them, maximum-likelihood and bootstrap, both widely used to
565 determine the b-value, showed acceptable errors (Bender, 1983; Bengoubou-Valérius & Gibert,
566 2013). This b-value points to the leading role of magmatic fluids, gases and/or magma, in the
567 seismicity, as reported in several volcanic areas (McNutt, 2004; Ibáñez et al., 2012; López et al.,
568 2017).

569

570 Besides the b-value for the first swarm, other important data must be taken into account. The
571 depth of seismicity matched the deepest magma storage level identified by Klügel et al. [2005]
572 on a petrological basis (A in Fig. 9a). At this depth, between 15 and 26 km (430 – 780 MPa),
573 clinopyroxenes showed a high degree of crystallization suggesting a long equilibrium period in
574 the range of years or decades. This indicates that magma intrusions beneath Cumbre Vieja
575 have usually halted at least once during their ascent, although several authors have reported a
576 multi-stop ascent, with up to three levels (Klügel et al., 2000, 2005; Galipp et al., 2006; Barker et
577 al., 2015).

578

579 On November 23 2017, the $(R/R_a)_c$ and CO_2 concentration rose at QP63 up to 7.94 ± 0.05 and
580 56.6 ± 3.0 % respectively (Figs. 4a and 4d). Recorded a month and a half after the first swarm,
581 these two increases were probably linked to new fractures associated with the seismicity, which
582 provided new ascent paths for magmatic gases as reported in other volcanic areas (Chiodini et
583 al., 2001; Granieri et al., 2003; Carapezza et al., 2009; Padrón et al., 2012) (Fig. 9b). As
584 mentioned, sampling point QP63 is located close to the area where the first swarm was located
585 and seems to provide a preferential path for magmatic deep gases, based on its $(R/R_a)_c$ and
586 $\delta^{13}C-CO_2$ values.

587

588 Therefore, the most plausible explanation for the dataset prior to October 2017 is an ascending
589 degassing magma batch from depth, and/or an active magma reservoir located at level A as
590 identified by Klügel et al. [2015], which has become destabilized (Phases A and B in Fig. 9).
591 This conclusion is based on: i) increased in $(R/R_a)_c$ at QP63 prior to October 2017 that could be
592 related to a magmatic gas input (Carapezza et al., 2004; Capasso et al., 2005b; Padrón et al.,
593 2013; Sano et al., 2015); ii) increases in $[H_2]$ at QP63 and $^4He_{crust}$ at QP60 attributable to a
594 microfracturing process due to increased tectonic stress (Ito et al., 1999; Moreira et al., 2003;
595 Saruwatari et al., 2004; Lowenstern et al., 2014); iii) a decrease in $(R/R_a)_c$ at QP60 due to

596 $^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$ (Tedesco, 1997; Capasso et al., 2005b; Padrón et al., 2013); iv) a b-value above the
597 pure tectonic value for the first swarm pointing to a contribution from magmatic fluids, gas
598 and/or magma (McNutt, 2004; Ibáñez et al., 2012; López et al., 2017); v) the seismicity depth
599 that matches the deepest magma stagnation level identified by several authors for historical
600 eruptions at La Palma (Klügel et al., 2005; Galipp et al., 2006; Barker et al., 2015); and vi)
601 increases in $(R/R_a)_c$ and $[\text{CO}_2]$ after the first swarm at the closest sampling point (QP63), which
602 may be linked to a growth in magmatic gas emission and/or fractures linked to seismicity that
603 provided new ascending paths for deep gases (Chiodini et al., 2001; Granieri et al., 2003;
604 Carapezza et al., 2009; Padrón et al., 2012).

605
606 Whether caused by a magmatic intrusion and/or an active reservoir, the intruded or expanded
607 volume can be estimated from the cumulative seismic moment of the volcano-tectonic (VT)
608 events (White & McCausland, 2016). To convert the mbLg magnitude of close volcano-tectonic
609 earthquakes to seismic moment, the equation reported by Hanks and Kanamori [1978] for
610 surface waves was applied. Following the procedure described in White & McCausland [2016],
611 based on VT events, an intruded volume of $1.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$ was estimated. If a stagnated
612 magmatic intrusion was the real situation, this estimated value would be only the volume
613 difference and not the entire volume.

614
615 In order to explain the seismicity depth, two factors may play an important role. First, since not
616 all magmatic intrusions reach the surface (Albert et al., 2015), and considering the eruptive
617 history of La Palma (Troll & Carracedo, 2016), the number of previous stalled magmatic
618 intrusions could be really high. Thus magma cooled at that depth may have created strength
619 barriers (Martí et al., 2016) against subsequent magma ascents (A in Fig. 9a). Second, for
620 peridotitic mantle xenoliths found in the San Juan lava flows (1949), Klügel et al. [1998]
621 suggested an origin related to fracturation of peridotite host-rock during magma ascent through
622 fractures and veins. In the same study, the authors estimate a 35 km depth for these xenoliths.
623 Afterwards, Klügel et al [2000] determined a 26-36 km depth range for the source of those
624 peridotitic xenoliths sampled in the last eruptive event during the San Juan episode, at El
625 Duraznero. Hence, taking into account these petrological results, fracturation of the host-rock in
626 the upper-most mantle could be another possible explanation for low magnitude seismicity in
627 October 2017 (Rubin, 1995). Hence, most likely one or a combination of the following two
628 scenarios could explain the swarm occurrence, its depth and low magnitude: i) previous
629 intrusions acting as strength barriers (Klügel, 1998; Klügel et al., 2000), ii) fracturation of the
630 peridotite host-rock in the upper-most mantle (Rubin, 1995; Klügel, 1998).

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Table 4. Phases identified and summary of their main geochemical and geophysical characteristics

Phase	(R/R _a) _c	δ ¹³ C-CO ₂ vs VPDB	[CO ₂]	[H ₂]	Thoron	S
A Prior to October 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decrease at QP60 from 9.95 ± 0.07 to 9.16 ± 0.07 in September 2017 Slight increase at QP63 up to 7.23 ± 0.05 in September 2017 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steady values at QP60 between -3.7 ± 0.1 ‰ and -3.4 ± 0.1 ‰ Mean value of -7.95 ± 0.1 ‰ at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Values below 23% ± 3 % at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On February 17 2017, 15 ± 0.8 ppm at QP63 On September 19 2017, 16 days before the first swarm, [H₂] reached 50.8 ± 2.5 ppm at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background level: 7 August 2017.
B October 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relative maximum of 7.94 ± 0.05 at QP63 on November 23, 2017 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slight drop at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum value of 56.6 ± 3.0 % at QP63 on November 23, 2017 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Base level of 1 ppm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background levels at QP40 and QP41 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 128 events Mean d b = 1.6 Mainly west fl
C February – March 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum at QP63, 8.23 ± 0.12, on March 8, 2018 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remains stable at QP63 around -8.4 ± 0.1 ‰ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slight decrease at QP60 Background levels at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two anomalous values on January 23, 20.5 ± 1.0, and on March 8, 31.8 ± 1.6 at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leap in concentration at QP40 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 84 events Mean d b = 2.3 Slight e
D April 2018 – January 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum value at QP60, 8.76 ± 0.08 Drop at QP63 to 6.35 ± 0.06 Similar trends at both points between March 2018 and January 2019 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mean value of 7.66 ± 0.1 ‰ at QP63 until August 2018 Afterwards, a decreasing trend at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Values around 97 % ± 3 % at QP60 Below 20% at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6.9 ± 0.4 and 11.7 ± 0.6 ppm in June and August 2018 respectively at QP63 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High level maintained at QP40 Slight increase at QP41 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 17 seis

639
 640 **Fig. 9.** Sketches showing east-west cross sections of Cumbre Vieja for each phase discussed in Section 5.1.
 641 Letters A, B and C stand for magma stagnation levels from Klügel et al. [2005].
 642

643

644 Regarding radon concentration at QP40, the increase in its mean concentration before and
 645 after the power-supply issue in November 2017 (Fig. 6a4) was most probably related to
 646 seasonal behavior, since the same change occurred in October 2018. Indeed, this increase
 647 in radon concentration appeared to respond to atmospheric temperature (Cigolini et al.,
 648 2009). When the temperature clearly dropped below 20 °C, radon concentration increased
 649 (Fig. 6a4).

650

651 At QP41, radon followed the same pattern (Fig 6b4). The constant increase in radon
 concentration after the first swarm matched the same increase from October 2018. As in

652 QP40, this seasonal pattern seemed to be governed by atmospheric temperature (Cigolini et
653 al., 2009), with increasing radon concentration when temperature decreased below 23 °C
654 approximately. Thoron concentration at QP40 exhibited the same behavior as radon (Fig.
655 6a5), a slight increase probably also due to the influence of atmospheric parameters.
656

657 As mentioned, in February 2018 a new seismic series took place, with at least 84 events
658 detected and located (Table 1). The second swarm released more seismic energy than the
659 first. Its b-value, 2.3 ± 0.2 , points to a higher magmatic fluid contribution in the seismicity
660 (McNutt, 1996; McNutt, 2005; Ibáñez et al., 2012; López et al., 2017). Seismicity was deeper,
661 and this fact was confirmed by $\Delta T_{S}T_P$ and relocation results (Fig. 2d and 3c). Moreover, an
662 eastward migration was not only reflected in raw seismicity location (white dots in Figs. 3a
663 and 3b), but also by the relocation result (Fig. 3c). This seismicity displacement was likely
664 related to the highly heterogeneous monogenetic volcanic fields at that depth, as mentioned.
665 During its ascent or destabilization, the magma may have encountered a strength barrier,
666 previous intrusion and/or high material heterogeneity (Klügel et al., 2005; Taisne et al., 2011;
667 Barker et al., 2015; Martí et al., 2016; Martí et al., 2017), making lateral movement easier
668 than vertical (Phase C in Fig. 9). A lateral magma movement is not unusual since it has been
669 described in other volcanic systems (Einarsson & Brandsdóttir, 1978; Peltier et al., 2007), for
670 instance the latest eruption in the Canary Islands, the submarine eruption at El Hierro (López
671 et al., 2012; González et al., 2013; Klügel et al., 2015; Martí et al., 2017). It even has been
672 suggested for La Palma based on petrological data (Klügel et al., 2000).
673

674 One more time, an increase in hydrogen concentration at QP63 was recorded, starting 18
675 days before the second swarm (Section 4.2 and Sampling data in Supplementary Material)
676 and reaching maximum on March 8, 2018. This increase, as also occurred in September
677 2017, was probably related to the stress-induced microfracturing and fractures associated
678 with seismic events (Ito et al., 1999; Saruwatari et al., 2004).
679

680 At this point, it would be desirable to estimate the shape of the magma intrusion, but ground
681 deformation data are normally required for that. Since no ground deformation was recorded
682 and taking into account an estimated 21-26 km intrusion depth between the swarms, the
683 lithostatic pressure and stress field at that depth would make the most probable intrusion
684 shape a dike or dikes (Rubin, 1995; Hansteen et al., 1998), or even a sill (Hansteen et al.,
685 1998; Gudmundsson, 2011). However, the intruded or expanded volume can be estimated
686 based on VT events following the same procedure as for the first swarm (White &
687 McCausland, 2016). Although the number of earthquakes was lower than in October 2017,
688 the magnitudes led to a great intruded volume, $3.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$. This result is practically double
689 that in the first swarm, which could suggest a greater magma displacement.
690

691 On March 8, 2018, QP63 reached its highest $(R/R_a)_c$ value (8.23 ± 0.12). It was the maximum
692 value in the entire record at that sampling point (Fig. 4a). Fractures linked to both swarms
693 probably facilitated a rapid gas ascent (Chiodini et al., 2001; Granieri et al., 2003; Carapezza
694 et al., 2009; Padrón et al., 2012) as occurred after the first swarm in November 2017.
695 Although the total number of earthquakes was lower in the second swarm, magnitudes were

696 higher (Table 1), involving longer fractures (Olson & Allen, 2005).

697

698 Afterwards, on April 4 2018, QP60 dropped to its minimum $(R/R_a)_c$ and QP63 also decreased
699 (Fig. 4a). At QP60, the $^4\text{He}_{\text{crust}}$ contribution was high on that date (Fig. 4b). These trends
700 were probably associated with the crustal stress and seismicity that occurred in February
701 2018, releasing radiogenic helium through fracturation (Capasso et al., 2005; Padrón et al.,
702 2013; Lowenstern et al., 2014) (dashed arrow in Fig. 9d). This stress, most likely related to
703 overpressure caused by the intruded magma, was also reflected in higher thoron
704 concentration at QP40 in February 2018 (Fig. 6a5).

705

706 At QP40 there was a leap in its concentration during February 2018, after the second swarm,
707 from a mean of $9 \pm 3 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ to $23 \pm 5 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ (Figs. 6a5). This sharp increase was confirmed
708 by replacing the radon/thoron monitor by another calibrated monitor in July 2018, obtaining
709 the same high concentration values (Section 4.2). Thus, it is possible to assert that the
710 increase in thoron concentration was real. This increase, related to tectonic stress, which
711 would cause microfracturing and release thoron from radium chain decay (Giammanco et al.,
712 2007; Tuccimei et al., 2010; Scarlato et al., 2013) (Phase D in Fig. 9). This process must
713 have been relatively shallow since thoron has a short half-life and no simultaneous radon
714 increase was recorded (Giammanco et al., 2007).

715

716 Thoron concentration at QP41 did not show any abrupt change after the second swarm, it is
717 noteworthy that its slight increase (Section 4.2), apparently uncorrelated with any
718 atmospheric parameter also suggests that the same process increase in tectonic stress
719 (Giammanco et al., 2007; Tuccimei et al., 2010; Scarlato et al., 2013), was taking place in the
720 southern part of Cumbre Vieja.

721

722 The slight eastward movement of seismicity (Section 4.1) could imply that the magma
723 migrated closer to the Cumbre Vieja rift axis. This area is highly fractured since it has hosted
724 many previous eruptions (Troll & Carracedo, 2016), providing preferential paths for deep gas
725 ascent (Padrón et al., 2012). In this way, magmatic gases found an easier way to reach the
726 surface through the rift zone, reflecting a gas-release migration towards the center of the
727 monogenetic field. This could explain the constant decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ at QP63, possibly
728 owing to a lesser input of deep gases and/or a higher biogenic contribution (Chiodini et al.,
729 2008; Padrón et al., 2015) (Fig. 4c and 5b). Gas migration towards the east may also explain
730 thoron concentration increases through time at QP40 and QP41 (Figures 6a5 and 6b5). After
731 the second swarm, these increases may be related to the slight growth in CO_2 flux acting as
732 a gas carrier (Neri et al., 2016) (Phase D in Fig. 9). This flux must have been small, since no
733 clear increase in radon concentration was recorded (Fig. 6a4 and 6b4) (Giammanco et al.,
734 2007). Previous or new fractures in the rift or changes in the stress field could have facilitated
735 CO_2 ascent (Neri et al., 2016; Falsaperla et al., 2017).

736

737 Radon at QP40 did not show any change that could be related to the February swarm.
738 Several months prior to the second swarm, it reached a maximum level that stayed around a
739 mean value of $599 \pm 160 \text{ Bq/m}^3$ until July 2018 (Fig. 6a4). Just after the second swarm,

740 radon increased sharply at QP41, reaching its maximum value before the monitoring system
741 failure (Fig. 6b4). This sharp increase was due to the rapid drop in barometric pressure
742 (Cigolini et al., 2009) and rainfall (Fig. 6b3). From July 2018 to October 2018, radon showed
743 a seasonal pattern with low concentrations during summer at both stations (Figs. 6a4 and
744 6b4), reflecting atmospheric temperature dependence as mentioned (Cigolini et al., 2009). It
745 is likely that the differences between radon levels during the two cold periods (October-July)
746 were linked with their different amounts of rainfall (black lines in Fig. 6a3 and 6b3) and hence,
747 different soil moistures (Laiolo et al., 2016).

748
749

750 What will happen next?

751 Addressing this question is difficult for two main reasons. The first is the inherent complexity
752 of monogenetic fields, and the second the scarce instrumental data on unrests and eruptions
753 in the Canary Islands, particularly for La Palma.

754 As mentioned in the previous sections, several authors have identified different stagnation
755 levels during magma ascent beneath Cumbre Vieja (Klügel et al., 2005; Galipp et al., 2006;
756 Barker et al., 2015). The data analyzed in this work suggest a magmatic intrusion and/or an
757 active magma reservoir at a depth that matches the deepest reported magma stagnation
758 level (level A in Fig. 9a). It is possible to assert that the unrest described here corresponds to
759 a stage previous to the underplating caused by magma stagnation (Barker et al., 2015;
760 Galipp et al., 2006; Klügel et al., 2005) (level B in Fig. 9a).

761 If a new magma intrusion took place, was this new batch of magma feeding a previous
762 reservoir or was it creating a new one? Based on the geochemical and geophysical data
763 reported here it is not possible to answer this question. However, taking into account that
764 seismicity has been monitored on La Palma since 1974 without any previously reported
765 seismic crisis (Section 4.1.1), this absence supports the idea of an incipient process.

766

767 If the magma stagnation process continues, it would not be surprising to record new unrest
768 periods like that described in this work, including seismicity and gas emissions. This may
769 occur in the coming years or decades according to the petrological data, since some authors
770 have reported magma stagnation times in this time range based on the growth equilibrium
771 time for clinopyroxene crystals at that depth (Klügel, 1998; Klügel et al., 2000, 2005; Barker
772 et al., 2015). Furthermore, if the stalled volume exceeds $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$ at that depth, ground
773 deformation would be detected by the GNSS network (Section 4.3).

774

775

776 6. Conclusions

777 Data analysis suggests that a deep magmatic intrusion took place beneath Cumbre Vieja,
778 and several results support this hypothesis.

779

780 The two seismic swarms had high b-values of 1.6 ± 0.1 and 2.3 ± 0.2 respectively, indicating
781 a major contribution of magmatic fluid contribution, gas and/or magma. Increase in
782 air-corrected helium isotopic ratio, $(R/R_a)_c$, from 6.10 ± 0.06 to 7.52 ± 0.05 and hydrogen
783 concentration were recorded several months prior to the first swarm at the closest sampling

784 point, QP63. This sampling point showed $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ values close to the MORB range
785 suggesting that QP63 was a preferential vent for deep magmatic gases. At the same site, an
786 anomalously high CO_2 concentration, $56.6 \pm 3.0 \%$, was registered between the two swarms,
787 October 2017 and February 2018. Additionally, before and after this last swarm an increase
788 in hydrogen concentration was recorded, and after each swarm, $(\text{R/R}_a)_c$ reached its
789 maximum values, 7.94 ± 0.05 on November 23, 2017 and 8.23 ± 0.12 on March 3, 2018,
790 once again at QP63.

791

792 Eastward magma migration towards Cumbre Vieja rift in February 2018 was deduced from
793 both raw seismicity location and relocation of swarms, and was reflected in the decreasing
794 $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ at QP63 after mid-2018. Since fracturing is more extensive in the rift zone, magma
795 migration could have increased CO_2 emission in that area after the second swarm. A leap in
796 thoron concentration at QP40 in February 2018 was recorded, supporting this hypothesis in
797 which, carbon dioxide acts as a carrier gas. Permanent increases in thoron background at
798 QP40 and QP41 support the mentioned growth in CO_2 emission, as does the finding that the
799 stress process is still going on, facilitating the shallow thoron release.

800

801 Although no ground deformation was observed, the maximum magma volume that could
802 intrude without being detected by the GNSS network was estimated. The result was a
803 maximum undetectable volume of $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$. On the other hand, the minimum intrusion
804 volumes based on the cumulative seismic moment of the volcano-tectonic events for both
805 swarms were calculated at $1.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$ and $3.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$ respectively, adding up to a total of
806 $5.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ km}^3$. Therefore, the true intrusion volume can be conjectured as between $5.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
807 km^3 and $3 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ km}^3$.

808

809 Finally, since the presented geophysical and geochemical data support this magmatic
810 intrusion, and the seismicity depth matched the deepest magma stagnation level reported for
811 the last two historical eruptions on La Palma (San Juan and Teneguía), it can be argued that
812 Cumbre Vieja is undergoing a reawakening process.

813

814 Taking into account the previously reported petrological results, and assuming that the
815 volcanic process is still going on, future unrest episodes should not be dismissed, nor even a
816 possible eruptive process. Although probably distant in time, in the range of several years to
817 even decades, this is a feasible scenario. For this reason, it is extremely important to
818 maintain a proper volcanic monitoring system at Cumbre Vieja, which includes increasing the
819 number of stations (seismic, geodesic and geochemical), and the number of gas sampling
820 points.

821

822

823 7. Declaration of interests

824 We declare there were no conflicting interests.

825

826

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837

838

839 9. Appendix: Sampling and analytical methods for the sites QP60 and QP63

840 During the whole sampling period care was taken to use always the same materials and also
841 to maintain constant sampling and analytical methods. Besides this, the field workers
842 responsible for taking the gas samples were always the same.

843

844 Bubbling gases (QP60) were sampled using an inverted funnel positioned above the
845 sampling point storing the gas in lead glass flasks equipped with two vacuum stopcocks.
846 Samples for dissolved gas analyses (QP63) were collected in 160 ml glass vials sealed
847 underwater with silicon/rubber septa using special pliers. All samples were collected with
848 care to avoid even the tiniest bubbles to prevent atmospheric contamination.

849

850 At the INGV laboratory in Palermo, the concentrations of He, H₂, and CO₂, in the samples
851 were determined by an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph equipped with a 4-m Carbosieve S
852 II and PoraPlot-U columns and a TCD detector using Ar as gas carrier. The analytical errors
853 were always within $\pm 5\%$ for He and H₂ and 3% for CO₂. Quantification limits were 1 ppm for
854 H₂, 2 ppm for He and 50 ppm for CO₂.

855

856 The bubbling gas samples were directly injected into the gas chromatograph, while dissolved
857 gas samples were extracted after equilibrium was reached at constant temperature with a
858 host-gas (high-purity Ar) injected into the sample bottle. The chemical composition of the
859 dissolved gas phase was obtained from the gas chromatographic analyses, taking into
860 account the solubility coefficients (Bunsen coefficient " β ", ccgas/mlwater STP) for each gas
861 species, the volume of gas extracted and the volume of the water sample (Giorgio Capasso
862 & Inguaggiato, 1998; Liotta & Martelli, 2012; Italiano et al., 2014). Starting from the total
863 amount of dissolved gases (ccSTP/L) we calculated the relative abundances for every single
864 gas species in equilibrium with the dissolved gas phase. The analytical results were
865 expressed in volumetric units (% or ppm), allowing the comparison of dissolved and free gas
866 results.

867

868 The ¹³C/¹²C ratios of CO₂ (expressed as $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ ‰ vs. VPDB) were measured with a
869 Finnigan Delta S mass spectrometer after purification of the gas mixture by standard
870 procedures using cryogenic traps (precisions ± 0.1 ‰). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of total dissolved
871 inorganic carbon (TDIC) were determined by acid extraction, following the method proposed

872 by Capasso et al. (2005). The theoretical carbon isotope composition of CO₂ in equilibrium
873 with the TDIC of the samples was calculated according to Zhang et al. (1995).

874

875 The abundance and isotope composition of He, and the ⁴He/²⁰Ne ratios, were determined by
876 separately admitting He and Ne into a split flight tube mass spectrometer (Helix SFT).
877 Similarly to the chemical analysis, the isotopic composition of He in the dissolved gas was
878 analyzed after equilibration with ultra-pure N₂ and extraction from the sampling bottle
879 headspace, as in the method of Inguaggiato and Rizzo (2004). Helium isotope compositions
880 are given as R/R_a, where R is the (³He/⁴He) ratio of the sample and R_a is the atmospheric
881 (³He/⁴He) ratio (R_a=1.386×10⁻⁶). The analytical errors were generally <1 %. Measured
882 values were corrected for atmospheric contamination of the sample (R/R_a)_c on the basis of its
883 ⁴He/²⁰Ne ratio (Sano & Wakita, 1985).

884

885 Samples were always sent by express courier to the laboratory and analyzed within two or
886 three weeks. As pointed out by Italiano et al. (2014), basing on laboratory tests and
887 theoretical diffusion data, errors introduced by such time intervals between sampling and
888 analysis are always well within the analytical error.

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898 References

899 Agencia Estatal de Meteorología. (2019). State Meteorological Agency - AEMET - Spanish

900 Government. Retrieved August 3, 2019, from <http://www.aemet.es/en/portada>

901 Aiuppa, A., Moretti, R., Federico, C., Giudice, G., Liuzzo, M., Gurrieri, S., et al. (2007).

902 Forecasting Etna eruptions by real-time observation of volcanic gas composition.

903 *Geology*, 35(12), 1115–1118. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G24149A.1>

904 Aki, K. (1965). Maximum likelihood estimate of b in the formula log N = a-bM and its

905 confidence limits. *Bull. Earthq. Res. Inst., Tokyo Univ.*, 43, 237–239.

906 Albert, H., Costa, F., & Martí, J. (2015). Timing of Magmatic Processes and Unrest

907 Associated with Mafic Historical Monogenetic Eruptions in Tenerife Island. *Journal*

908 *of Petrology*, 56(10), 1945–1966. <https://doi.org/10.1093/petrology/egv058>

909 Albert, H., Costa, F., & Martí, J. (2016). Years to weeks of seismic unrest and magmatic
910 intrusions precede monogenetic eruptions. *Geology*, 44(3), 211–214.
911 <https://doi.org/10.1130/G37239.1>

912 Altamimi, Z., Rebischung, P., Métivier, L., & Collilieux, X. (2016). ITRF2014: A new
913 release of the International Terrestrial Reference Frame modeling nonlinear station
914 motions. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 121(8), 6109–6131.
915 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JB013098>

916 Ancochea, E., Hernán, F., Cendrero, A., Cantagrel, J. M., Fúster, J., Ibarrola, E., & Coello, J.
917 (1994). Constructive and destructive episodes in the building of a young Oceanic
918 Island, La Palma, Canary Islands, and genesis of the Caldera de Taburiente. *Journal*
919 *of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 60(3), 243–262.
920 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0273\(94\)90054-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0273(94)90054-X)

921 Ballentine, C. J., Burgess, R., & Marty, B. (2002). Tracing Fluid Origin, Transport and
922 Interaction in the Crust. *Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry*, 47(1), 539–614.
923 <https://doi.org/10.2138/rmg.2002.47.13>

924 Barker, A. K., Troll, V. R., Carracedo, J. C., & Nicholls, P. A. (2015). The magma plumbing
925 system for the 1971 Teneguía eruption on La Palma, Canary Islands. *Contributions to*
926 *Mineralogy and Petrology*, 170(5), 54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-015-1207-7>

927 Bender, B. (1983). Maximum likelihood estimation of b values for magnitude grouped data.
928 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 73(3), 831–851.

929 Bengoubou-Valérius, M., & Gibert, D. (2013). Bootstrap determination of the reliability of

930 b-values: an assessment of statistical estimators with synthetic magnitude series.
931 *Natural Hazards*, 65(1), 443–459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-012-0376-1>

932 Boué, A., Lesage, P., Cortés, G., Valette, B., & Reyes-Dávila, G. (2015). Real-time eruption
933 forecasting using the material Failure Forecast Method with a Bayesian approach.
934 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 120(4), 2143–2161.
935 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JB011637>

936 Bridges, D. L., & Gao, S. S. (2006). Spatial variation of seismic b-values beneath Makushin
937 Volcano, Unalaska Island, Alaska. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 245(1),
938 408–415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2006.03.010>

939 Capasso, G., Carapezza, M. L., Federico, C., Inguaggiato, S., & Rizzo, A. (2005).
940 Geochemical monitoring of the 2002–2003 eruption at Stromboli volcano (Italy):
941 precursory changes in the carbon and helium isotopic composition of fumarole gases
942 and thermal waters. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 68(2), 118–134.
943 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-005-0427-5>

944 Capasso, G., Favara, R., Grassa, F., Inguaggiato, S., & Longo, L. (2005). On-line technique
945 for preparing and measuring stable carbon isotope of total dissolved inorganic
946 carbon in water samples ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{TDIC}}$). *Annals of Geophysics; Vol 48, No 1 (2005)*.
947 <https://doi.org/10.4401/ag-3190>

948 Capasso, Giorgio, & Inguaggiato, S. (1998). A simple method for the determination of
949 dissolved gases in natural waters. An application to thermal waters from Vulcano
950 Island. *Applied Geochemistry*, 13(5), 631–642.
951 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-2927\(97\)00109-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-2927(97)00109-1)

952 Carapezza, M., Inguaggiato, S., Brusca, L., & Longo, M. (2004). Geochemical precursors of
953 the activity of an open-conduit volcano: The Stromboli 2002-2003 eruptive events,
954 31. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GL019614>

955 Carapezza, M. L., Ricci, T., Ranaldi, M., & Tarchini, L. (2009). Active degassing structures
956 of Stromboli and variations in diffuse CO₂ output related to the volcanic activity. *The*
957 *2007 Eruption of Stromboli*, 182(3), 231–245.
958 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2008.08.006>

959 Carracedo, J. C., Day, S., Guillou, H., Rodríguez Badiola, E., Canas, J. A., & Pérez Torrado,
960 F. J. (1998). Hotspot volcanism close to a passive continental margin: the Canary
961 Islands. *Geological Magazine*, 135(5), 591–604.
962 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016756898001447>

963 Carracedo, J. C., Badiola, E. R., Guillou, H., & Torrado, F. J. P. (2001). Geology and
964 volcanology of La Palma and El Hierro, Western Canaries. *Estudios Geológicos*,
965 57(5–6). <https://doi.org/10.3989/egeol.01575-6134>

966 Chiodini, G., Frondini, F., Cardellini, C., Granieri, D., Marini, L., & Ventura, G. (2001). CO₂
967 degassing and energy release at Solfatara volcano, Campi Flegrei, Italy. *Journal of*
968 *Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 106(B8), 16213–16221.
969 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JB000246>

970 Chiodini, G., Caliro, S., Cardellini, C., Avino, R., Granieri, D., & Schmidt, A. (2008).
971 Carbon isotopic composition of soil CO₂ efflux, a powerful method to discriminate
972 different sources feeding soil CO₂ degassing in volcanic-hydrothermal areas. *Earth*
973 *and Planetary Science Letters*, 274(3), 372–379.

974 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2008.07.051>

975 Cigolini, C., Poggi, P., Ripepe, M., Laiolo, M., Ciamberlini, C., Donne, D. D., et al. (2009).
976 Radon surveys and real-time monitoring at Stromboli volcano: Influence of soil
977 temperature, atmospheric pressure and tidal forces on ^{222}Rn degassing. *Journal of*
978 *Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 184(3), 381–388.
979 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2009.04.019>

980 Cruz-Reyna, S. D. la, & Yokoyama, I. (2011). A geophysical characterization of monogenetic
981 volcanism. *Geofísica Internacional*, 50, 465–484.

982 Dach, R., Andritsch, F., Arnold, D., Bertone, S., Fridez, P., Jäggi, A., et al. (2015). *Bernese*
983 *GNSS Software Version 5.2*. <https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.72297>

984 Dañobeitia, J. J., Udias Vallina, A., & Universidad Complutense de Madrid. Facultad de
985 Ciencias Físicas. Departamento de Física de la Tierra, A. y A. I. (1985). *Estudio*
986 *geofísico submarino en el area del Archipiélago Canario*. Retrieved from
987 WorldCat.org.

988 Das, D., & Veziroğlu, T. N. (2001). Hydrogen production by biological processes: a survey
989 of literature. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 26(1), 13–28.
990 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-3199\(00\)00058-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-3199(00)00058-6)

991 Day, J. M. D., & Hilton, D. R. (2011). Origin of $3\text{He}/4\text{He}$ ratios in HIMU-type basalts
992 constrained from Canary Island lavas. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 305(1),
993 226–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2011.03.006>

994 Day, S. J., Carracedo, J. C., Guillou, H., & Gravestock, P. (1999). Recent structural evolution
995 of the Cumbre Vieja volcano, La Palma, Canary Islands: volcanic rift zone

996 reconfiguration as a precursor to volcano flank instability? *Journal of Volcanology*
997 *and Geothermal Research*, 94(1), 135–167.
998 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273\(99\)00101-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273(99)00101-8)

999 DeMets, C., Gordon, R. G., Argus, D. F., & Stein, S. (1994). Effect of recent revisions to the
1000 geomagnetic reversal time scale on estimates of current plate motions. *Geophysical*
1001 *Research Letters*, 21(20), 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1029/94GL02118>

1002 Derwent, R. G., Simmonds, P. G., O’Doherty, S. J., Manning, A. J., & Spain, T. G. (2019). A
1003 24-year record of high-frequency, in situ, observations of hydrogen at the
1004 Atmospheric Research Station at Mace Head, Ireland. *Atmospheric Environment*, 203,
1005 28–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.01.050>

1006 Efron, B. (1982). *The Jackknife, the Bootstrap and Other Resampling Plans*. Society for
1007 Industrial and Applied Mathematics. <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9781611970319>

1008 Einarsson, P., & Brandsdottir, B. (1978). *Seismological evidence for Lateral magma*
1009 *intrusion during the July 1978 deflation of the Krafla volcano in NE-Iceland*. United
1010 States. <https://doi.org/10.2172/890964>

1011 Falsaperla, S., Behncke, B., Langer, H., Neri, M., Salerno, G. G., Giammanco, S., et al.
1012 (2014). “Failed” eruptions revealed by pattern classification analysis of gas emission
1013 and volcanic tremor data at Mt. Etna, Italy. *International Journal of Earth Sciences*,
1014 103(1), 297–313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00531-013-0964-7>

1015 Falsaperla, S., Neri, M., Di Grazia, G., Langer, H., & Spampinato, S. (2017). What happens
1016 to in-soil Radon activity during a long-lasting eruption? Insights from Etna by
1017 multidisciplinary data analysis. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 18(6),

1018 2162–2176. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GC006825>

1019 Friedman, A. R., Reverdin, G., Khodri, M., & Gastineau, G. (2017). A new record of Atlantic
1020 sea surface salinity from 1896 to 2013 reveals the signatures of climate variability
1021 and long-term trends. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *44*(4), 1866–1876.
1022 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL072582>

1023 Galipp, K., Klügel, A., & Hansteen, T. H. (2006). Changing depths of magma fractionation
1024 and stagnation during the evolution of an oceanic island volcano: La Palma (Canary
1025 Islands). *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, *155*(3), 285–306.
1026 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2006.04.002>

1027 Giammanco, S., Sims, K. W. W., & Neri, M. (2007). Measurements of ^{220}Rn and ^{222}Rn and
1028 CO_2 emissions in soil and fumarole gases on Mt. Etna volcano (Italy): Implications
1029 for gas transport and shallow ground fracture. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*,
1030 *8*(10). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GC001644>

1031 González, P. J., Tiampo, K. F., Camacho, A. G., & Fernández, J. (2010). Shallow flank
1032 deformation at Cumbre Vieja volcano (Canary Islands): Implications on the stability
1033 of steep-sided volcano flanks at oceanic islands. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*,
1034 *297*(3), 545–557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2010.07.006>

1035 González, P. J., Samsonov, S. V., Pepe, S., Tiampo, K. F., Tizzani, P., Casu, F., et al. (2013).
1036 Magma storage and migration associated with the 2011–2012 El Hierro eruption:
1037 Implications for crustal magmatic systems at oceanic island volcanoes. *Journal of*
1038 *Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, *118*(8), 4361–4377.
1039 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrb.50289>

1040 GRAFCAN. (2019). Estaciones GNSS de Canarias. Retrieved February 11, 2019, from
1041 https://idecan2.grafcan.es/ServicioWMS/GNSS?&SERVICE=WMS&SRS=EPSG:32628&VERSION=1.1.1&REQUEST=GetFeatureInfo&STYLES=&X=335&Y=225&BBOX=22699.458157305082,2953559.870667103,820419.5218426948,3307830.6493328963&WIDTH=1306&HEIGHT=580&QUERY_LAYERS=Estaciones&LAYER=Estaciones&INFO_FORMAT=text/html&FORMAT=image/png
1042
1043
1044
1045

1046 Graham, D. (2002). Noble gases in MORB and OIB: observational constraints for the
1047 characterization of mantle source reservoirs. *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.*, *46*, 247–318.

1048 Granieri, D., Chiodini, G., Marzocchi, W., & Avino, R. (2003). Continuous monitoring of
1049 CO₂ soil diffuse degassing at Phlegraean Fields (Italy): influence of environmental
1050 and volcanic parameters. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, *212*(1), 167–179.
1051 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(03\)00232-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(03)00232-2)

1052 Gudmundsson, A. (2011). Deflection of dykes into sills at discontinuities and
1053 magma-chamber formation. *Emplacement of Magma Pulses and Growth of Magma
1054 Bodies*, *500*(1), 50–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tecto.2009.10.015>

1055 Gutenberg, B., & Richter, C. F. (1944). Frequency of earthquakes in California*. *Bulletin of
1056 the Seismological Society of America*, *34*(4), 185–188.

1057 Gutenberg, Beno, & Richter, C. F. (1956). Magnitude and energy of earthquakes. *Annals of
1058 Geophysics; Vol 53, No 1 (2010)*. <https://doi.org/10.4401/ag-4588>

1059 Hansteen, T. H., Klügel, A., & Schmincke, H.-U. (1998). Multi-stage magma ascent beneath
1060 the Canary Islands: evidence from fluid inclusions. *Contributions to Mineralogy and
1061 Petrology*, *132*(1), 48–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004100050404>

1062 Hasenaka, T., & S.E. Carmichael, I. (1985). *The cinder cones of Michoacán-Guanajuato,*
1063 *central Mexico: their age, volume and distribution, and magma discharge rate* (Vol.
1064 25). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0273\(85\)90007-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0273(85)90007-1)

1065 Hausen, H. M. (1969). *Some Contributions to the Geology of La Palma (Canary Islands) &*
1066 *Hans Hausen.* Soc. Scientiarum Fennica.

1067 Hilton, D. R., Macpherson, C. G., & Elliott, T. R. (2000). Helium isotope ratios in mafic
1068 phenocrysts and geothermal fluids from La Palma, the Canary Islands (Spain):
1069 implications for HIMU mantle sources. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 64(12),
1070 2119–2132. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7037\(00\)00358-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7037(00)00358-6)

1071 Ibáñez, J. M., De Angelis, S., Díaz-Moreno, A., Hernández, P., Alguacil, G., Posadas, A., &
1072 Pérez, N. (2012). Insights into the 2011–2012 submarine eruption off the coast of El
1073 Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain) from statistical analyses of earthquake activity.
1074 *Geophysical Journal International*, 191(2), 659–670.
1075 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.2012.05629.x>

1076 IGME. (2010). Mapa Geológico de la Isla de La Palma a escala 1:100.000. Retrieved July 31,
1077 2019, from
1078 [http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/mapa.aspx?parent=../geologica/geolog](http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/mapa.aspx?parent=../geologica/geologiairegional.aspx&Id=6&language=es)
1079 [iairegional.aspx&Id=6&language=es](http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/mapa.aspx?parent=../geologica/geologiairegional.aspx&Id=6&language=es)

1080 IGN, I. G. N. (2019a). Instituto Geográfico Nacional. Retrieved February 11, 2019, from
1081 <http://www.ign.es>

1082 IGN, I. G. N. (2019b). Instituto Geográfico Nacional - Catalog.
1083 <https://doi.org/10.7914/SN/ES>

- 1084 Inguaggiato, S., & Rizzo, A. (2004). Dissolved helium isotope ratios in ground-waters: a new
1085 technique based on gas–water re-equilibration and its application to Stromboli
1086 volcanic system. *Applied Geochemistry*, 19(5), 665–673.
1087 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2003.10.009>
- 1088 Italiano, F., Yuce, G., Uysal, I. T., Gasparon, M., & Morelli, G. (2014). Insights into
1089 mantle-type volatiles contribution from dissolved gases in artesian waters of the
1090 Great Artesian Basin, Australia. *Chemical Geology*, 378–379, 75–88.
1091 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2014.04.013>
- 1092 Ito, T., Nagamine, K., Yamamoto, K., Adachi, M., & Kawabe, I. (1999). Preseismic hydrogen
1093 gas anomalies caused by stress-corrosion process preceding earthquakes.
1094 *Geophysical Research Letters*, 26(13), 2009–2012.
1095 <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999GL900407>
- 1096 Kanda, W., Utsugi, M., Tanaka, Y., Hashimoto, T., Fujii, I., Hasenaka, T., & Shigeno, N.
1097 (2010). A heating process of Kuchi-erabu-jima volcano, Japan, as inferred from
1098 geomagnetic field variations and electrical structure. *Journal of Volcanology and*
1099 *Geothermal Research*, 189(1), 158–171.
1100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2009.11.002>
- 1101 Kirk, J. T. (1994). *Light and photosynthesis in aquatic ecosystems*. Cambridge university
1102 press.
- 1103 Klügel, A. (1998). Reactions between mantle xenoliths and host magma beneath La Palma
1104 (Canary Islands): constraints on magma ascent rates and crustal reservoirs.
1105 *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*, 131(2), 237–257.

1106 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004100050391>

1107 Klügel, A., Hansteen, T. H., & Schmincke, H.-U. (1997). Rates of magma ascent and depths
1108 of magma reservoirs beneath La Palma (Canary Islands). *Terra Nova*, 9(3), 117–121.
1109 <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3121.1997.d01-15.x>

1110 Klügel, A., Hoernle, K. A., Schmincke, H.-U., & White, J. D. L. (2000). The chemically
1111 zoned 1949 eruption on La Palma (Canary Islands): Petrologic evolution and magma
1112 supply dynamics of a rift zone eruption. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid
1113 Earth*, 105(B3), 5997–6016. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JB900334>

1114 Klügel, A., Hansteen, T. H., & Galipp, K. (2005). Magma storage and underplating beneath
1115 Cumbre Vieja volcano, La Palma (Canary Islands). *Earth and Planetary Science
1116 Letters*, 236(1), 211–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2005.04.006>

1117 Klügel, A., Longpré, M.-A., García-Cañada, L., & Stix, J. (2015). Deep intrusions, lateral
1118 magma transport and related uplift at ocean island volcanoes. *Earth and Planetary
1119 Science Letters*, 431, 140–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2015.09.031>

1120 Laiolo, M., Ranaldi, M., Tarchini, L., Carapezza, M. L., Coppola, D., Ricci, T., & Cigolini, C.
1121 (2016). The effects of environmental parameters on diffuse degassing at Stromboli
1122 volcano: Insights from joint monitoring of soil CO₂ flux and radon activity. *Journal
1123 of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 315, 65–78.
1124 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2016.02.004>

1125 Lamolda, H., Felpeto, A., & Bethencourt, A. (2017). Time lag between deformation and
1126 seismicity along monogenetic volcanic unrest periods: The case of El Hierro Island
1127 (Canary Islands). *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44(13), 6771–6777.

- 1128 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL074494>
- 1129 Lee, S., Kang, N., Park, M., Hwang, J. Y., Yun, S. H., & Jeong, H. Y. (2018). A review on
1130 volcanic gas compositions related to volcanic activities and non-volcanological
1131 effects. *Geosciences Journal*, 22(1), 183–197.
1132 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12303-017-0056-y>
- 1133 Liotta, M., & Martelli, M. (2012). Dissolved gases in brackish thermal waters: an improved
1134 analytical method. *Geofluids*, 12(3), 236–244.
1135 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-8123.2012.00365.x>
- 1136 López Acevedo, F. J., Pellicer Bautista, M. J., & others. (2014). Uso de Sistemas de
1137 Información Geográfica para el cálculo del volumen de los materiales emitidos en la
1138 erupción de 1971 del volcán Teneguía (La Palma, Islas Canarias).
- 1139 López, C., Blanco, M. J., Abella, R., Brenes, B., Cabrera Rodríguez, V. M., Casas, B., et al.
1140 (2012). Monitoring the volcanic unrest of El Hierro (Canary Islands) before the onset
1141 of the 2011–2012 submarine eruption. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 39(13), n/a–n/a.
1142 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL051846>
- 1143 López, Carmen, Benito-Saz, M. A., Martí, J., del-Fresno, C., García-Cañada, L., Albert, H.,
1144 & Lamolda, H. (2017). Driving magma to the surface: The 2011–2012 El Hierro
1145 Volcanic Eruption. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 18(8), 3165–3184.
1146 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GC007023>
- 1147 Lowenstern, J. B., Evans, W. C., Bergfeld, D., & Hunt, A. G. (2014). Prodigious degassing of
1148 a billion years of accumulated radiogenic helium at Yellowstone. *Nature*, 506, 355.
- 1149 Lyard, F., Lefevre, F., Letellier, T., & Francis, O. (2006). Modelling the global ocean tides:

1150 modern insights from FES2004. *Ocean Dynamics*, 56(5), 394–415.
1151 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-006-0086-x>

1152 Martí, J., López, C., Bartolini, S., Becerril, L., & Geyer, A. (2016). Stress Controls of
1153 Monogenetic Volcanism: A Review. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 4, 106.
1154 <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2016.00106>

1155 Martí, J., Villaseñor, A., Geyer, A., López, C., & Tryggvason, A. (2017). Stress barriers
1156 controlling lateral migration of magma revealed by seismic tomography. *Scientific
1157 Reports*, 7, 40757.

1158 Marzocchi, W., & Sandri, L. (2003). A review and new insights on the estimation of the
1159 b-value and its uncertainty. *Annals of Geophysics; Vol 46, No 6 (2003)DO -
1160 10.4401/Ag-3472*. Retrieved from
1161 <https://www.annalsofgeophysics.eu/index.php/annals/article/view/3472>

1162 McNutt, S. R. (1996). Seismic Monitoring and Eruption Forecasting of Volcanoes: A Review
1163 of the State-of-the-Art and Case Histories. In R. Scarpa & R. I. Tilling (Eds.),
1164 *Monitoring and Mitigation of Volcano Hazards* (pp. 99–146). Berlin, Heidelberg:
1165 Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-80087-0_3

1166 McNutt, Stephen R. (2005). VOLCANIC SEISMOLOGY. *Annual Review of Earth and
1167 Planetary Sciences*, 33(1), 461–491.
1168 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.earth.33.092203.122459>

1169 Melián, G., Tassi, F., Pérez, N., Hernández, P., Sortino, F., Vaselli, O., et al. (2012). A
1170 magmatic source for fumaroles and diffuse degassing from the summit crater of Teide
1171 Volcano (Tenerife, Canary Islands): a geochemical evidence for the 2004–2005

1172 seismic–volcanic crisis. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 74(6), 1465–1483.
1173 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-012-0613-1>

1174 Mogi, K. (1958). Relations between the eruptions of various volcanoes and the deformations
1175 of the ground surfaces around them. *Bull. Earthq. Res. Inst.*, 36, 99–134.

1176 Moran, S. C., Newhall, C., & Roman, D. C. (2011). Failed magmatic eruptions: late-stage
1177 cessation of magma ascent. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 73(2), 115–122.
1178 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-010-0444-x>

1179 Moreira, M., Blusztajn, J., Curtice, J., Hart, S., Dick, H., & Kurz, M. D. (2003). He and Ne
1180 isotopes in oceanic crust: implications for noble gas recycling in the mantle. *Earth
1181 and Planetary Science Letters*, 216(4), 635–643.
1182 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(03\)00554-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(03)00554-5)

1183 National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, & Medicine. (2017). *Volcanic Eruptions and
1184 Their Repose, Unrest, Precursors, and Timing*. Washington, DC: The National
1185 Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24650>

1186 Nava, F. A., Márquez-Ramírez, V. H., Zúñiga, F. R., Ávila-Barrientos, L., & Quinteros, C. B.
1187 (2017). Gutenberg-Richter b-value maximum likelihood estimation and sample size.
1188 *Journal of Seismology*, 21(1), 127–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10950-016-9589-1>

1189 Needham, A. J., Lindsay, J. M., Smith, I. E. M., Augustinus, P., & Shane, P. A. (2011).
1190 Sequential eruption of alkaline and sub-alkaline magmas from a small monogenetic
1191 volcano in the Auckland Volcanic Field, New Zealand. *From Maars to Scoria Cones:
1192 The Enigma of Monogenetic Volcanic Fields*, 201(1), 126–142.
1193 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2010.07.017>

- 1194 Neri, M., Ferrera, E., Giammanco, S., Currenti, G., Cirrincione, R., Patanè, G., & Zanon, V.
1195 (2016). Soil radon measurements as a potential tracer of tectonic and volcanic activity.
1196 *Scientific Reports*, 6, 24581.
- 1197 Olson, E. L., & Allen, R. M. (2005). The deterministic nature of earthquake rupture. *Nature*,
1198 438(7065), 212–215. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04214>
- 1199 Padrón, E., Pérez, N. M., Hernández, P. A., Sumino, H., Melián, G., Barrancos, J., et al.
1200 (2012). Helium emission at Cumbre Vieja volcano, La Palma, Canary Islands.
1201 *Chemical Geology*, 312–313, 138–147.
1202 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2012.04.018>
- 1203 Padrón, E., Pérez, N. M., Hernández, P. A., Sumino, H., Melián, G. V., Barrancos, J., et al.
1204 (2013). Diffusive helium emissions as a precursory sign of volcanic unrest. *Geology*,
1205 41(5), 539–542. <https://doi.org/10.1130/G34027.1>
- 1206 Padrón, E., Pérez, N. M., Rodríguez, F., Melián, G., Hernández, P. A., Sumino, H., et al.
1207 (2015). Dynamics of diffuse carbon dioxide emissions from Cumbre Vieja volcano,
1208 La Palma, Canary Islands. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 77(4), 28.
1209 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-015-0914-2>
- 1210 Paonita, A., Caracausi, A., Iacono-Marziano, G., Martelli, M., & Rizzo, A. (2012).
1211 Geochemical evidence for mixing between fluids exsolved at different depths in the
1212 magmatic system of Mt Etna (Italy). *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 84, 380–394.
1213 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2012.01.028>
- 1214 Peltier, A., Staudacher, T., & Bachèlery, P. (2007). Constraints on magma transfers and
1215 structures involved in the 2003 activity at Piton de La Fournaise from displacement

1216 data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 112(B3).
1217 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JB004379>

1218 Pérez, N. M. (1994). $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ Isotopic Ratios in Volcanic-Hydrothermal Discharges from
1219 the Canary Islands, Spain: Implications on the Origin of the Volcanic Activity.
1220 *Mineralogical Magazine*, 58, 709–710.
1221 <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1994.58A.2.107>

1222 Pérez-López, R., Legrand, D., Garduño-Monroy, V. H., Rodríguez-Pascua, M. A., &
1223 Giner-Robles, J. L. (2011). Scaling laws of the size-distribution of monogenetic
1224 volcanoes within the Michoacán-Guanajuato Volcanic Field (Mexico). *From Maars*
1225 *to Scoria Cones: The Enigma of Monogenetic Volcanic Fields*, 201(1), 65–72.
1226 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2010.09.006>

1227 Phillipson, G., Sobradelo, R., & Gottsmann, J. (2013). Global volcanic unrest in the 21st
1228 century: An analysis of the first decade. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal*
1229 *Research*, 264, 183–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2013.08.004>

1230 Pineau, F., & Javoy, M. (1983). Carbon isotopes and concentrations in mid-oceanic ridge
1231 basalts. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 62(2), 239–257.
1232 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X\(83\)90087-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X(83)90087-0)

1233 Romero Ruiz, C. (1989). *Las manifestaciones volcánicas históricas del Archipiélago*
1234 *Canario*. Tesis Universidad de La Laguna., La Laguna.

1235 Rubin, A. M. (1995). Propagation of Magma-Filled Cracks. *Annual Review of Earth and*
1236 *Planetary Sciences*, 23(1), 287–336.
1237 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ea.23.050195.001443>

1238 Rubio, J. M. B. (1950). *Contribución al estudio de la erupción del volcán del Nambroque o*
1239 *San Juan (Isla de La Palma): 24 de junio-4 de agosto de 1949*. Instituto Geográfico y
1240 Catastral.

1241 Sainz-Maza Aparicio, S., Arnosó Sampedro, J., González Montesinos, F., & Martí Molist, J.
1242 (2014). Volcanic signatures in time gravity variations during the volcanic unrest on El
1243 Hierro (Canary Islands). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, *119*(6),
1244 5033–5051. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JB010795>

1245 Sakamoto, M., Sano, Y., & Wakita, H. (1992). $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratio distribution in and around the
1246 Hakone volcano. *GEOCHEMICAL JOURNAL*, *26*(4), 189–195.
1247 <https://doi.org/10.2343/geochemj.26.189>

1248 Sano, Y., & Wakita, H. (1985). Geographical distribution of $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios in Japan:
1249 Implications for arc tectonics and incipient magmatism. *Journal of Geophysical*
1250 *Research: Solid Earth*, *90*(B10), 8729–8741.
1251 <https://doi.org/10.1029/JB090iB10p08729>

1252 Sano, Y., Kagoshima, T., Takahata, N., Nishio, Y., Rouilleau, E., Pinti, D. L., & Fischer, T. P.
1253 (2015). Ten-year helium anomaly prior to the 2014 Mt Ontake eruption. *Scientific*
1254 *Reports*, *5*, 13069.

1255 Santerre, R. (1991). Impact of GPS satellite sky distribution.

1256 Saruwatari, K., Kameda, J., & Tanaka, H. (2004). Generation of hydrogen ions and hydrogen
1257 gas in quartz–water crushing experiments: an example of chemical processes in
1258 active faults. *Physics and Chemistry of Minerals*, *31*(3), 176–182.
1259 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-004-0382-2>

- 1260 Scarlato, P., Tuccimei, P., Mollo, S., Soligo, M., & Castelluccio, M. (2013). Contrasting
1261 radon background levels in volcanic settings: clues from ^{220}Rn activity concentrations
1262 measured during long-term deformation experiments. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 75(9),
1263 751. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-013-0751-0>
- 1264 Schmincke, H.-U., Klügel, A., Hansteen, T. H., Hoernle, K., & van den Bogaard, P. (1998).
1265 Samples from the Jurassic ocean crust beneath Gran Canaria, La Palma and
1266 Lanzarote (Canary Islands). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 163(1–4), 343–360.
1267 [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0012-821x\(98\)00168-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0012-821x(98)00168-x)
- 1268 Schultz, R., Stern, V., & Gu, Y. J. (2014). An investigation of seismicity clustered near the
1269 Cordel Field, west central Alberta, and its relation to a nearby disposal well. *Journal*
1270 *of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 119(4), 3410–3423.
1271 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JB010836>
- 1272 Shi, Y., & Bolt, B. A. (1982). The standard error of the magnitude-frequency b value.
1273 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 72(5), 1677–1687.
- 1274 Smith, J. O. (2007). *Introduction to Digital Filters: With Audio Applications*. W3K.
1275 Retrieved from <https://books.google.es/books?id=pC1iCQUAsHEC>
- 1276 Staudigel, H., & Schmincke, H.-U. (1984). The Pliocene seamount series of La
1277 Palma/Canary Islands. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 89(B13),
1278 11195–11215. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JB089iB13p11195>
- 1279 Stephens, K. J., Ebmeier, S. K., Young, N. K., & Biggs, J. (2017). Transient deformation
1280 associated with explosive eruption measured at Masaya volcano (Nicaragua) using
1281 Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar. *Volcano Geodesy: Recent Developments*

1282 *and Future Challenges*, 344, 212–223.
1283 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2017.05.014>

1284 Sweeney, C., Newberger, T., Munro, D. R., & others. (2016). A multi-decade record of
1285 high-quality fCO₂ data in version 3 of the Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas (SOCAT).
1286 *Earth System Science Data*, 8(2).

1287 Taisne, B., Tait, S., & Jaupart, C. (2011). Conditions for the arrest of a vertical propagating
1288 dyke. *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 73(2), 191–204.
1289 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00445-010-0440-1>

1290 Tedesco, D. (1997). Systematic variations in the ³He/⁴He ratio and carbon of fumarolic
1291 fluids from active volcanic areas in Italy: Evidence for radiogenic ⁴He and crustal
1292 carbon addition by the subducting African plate? *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*,
1293 151(3), 255–269. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(97\)81852-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(97)81852-3)

1294 Troll, V. R., & Carracedo, J. C. (2016). Chapter 3 - The Geology of La Palma. In *The*
1295 *Geology of the Canary Islands* (pp. 101–180). Elsevier.
1296 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809663-5.00003-7>

1297 Tuccimei, P., Mollo, S., Vinciguerra, S., Castelluccio, M., & Soligo, M. (2010). Radon and
1298 thoron emission from lithophysae-rich tuff under increasing deformation: An
1299 experimental study. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37(5).
1300 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GL042134>

1301 Waldhauser, F. (2001). *hypoDD -- A program to compute double-difference hypocenter*
1302 *locations (hypoDD version 1.0 - 03/2001)*.

1303 Waldhauser, F., & Ellsworth, W. L. (2000). A Double-difference Earthquake location

1304 algorithm: Method and application to the Northern Hayward Fault, California.
1305 *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 90(6), 1353–1368.
1306 <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120000006>

1307 Ward, S. N., & Day, S. (2001). Cumbre Vieja Volcano—Potential collapse and tsunami at La
1308 Palma, Canary Islands. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 28(17), 3397–3400.
1309 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001GL013110>

1310 Wawrzyniak, P., Zlotnicki, J., Sailhac, P., & Marquis, G. (2017). Resistivity variations related
1311 to the large March 9, 1998 eruption at La Fournaise volcano inferred by continuous
1312 MT monitoring. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 347, 185–206.
1313 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2017.09.011>

1314 White, R., & McCausland, W. (2016). Volcano-tectonic earthquakes: A new tool for
1315 estimating intrusive volumes and forecasting eruptions. *Journal of Volcanology and*
1316 *Geothermal Research*, 309, 139–155.
1317 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2015.10.020>

1318 Zeebe, R. E., & Wolf-Gladrow, D. (2001). *CO2 in seawater: equilibrium, kinetics, isotopes*.
1319 Gulf Professional Publishing.

1320 Zhang, J., Quay, P. D., & Wilbur, D. O. (1995). Carbon isotope fractionation during
1321 gas-water exchange and dissolution of CO2. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*,
1322 59(1), 107–114. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037\(95\)91550-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037(95)91550-D)

1323 Zhou, Y., Zhou, S., & Zhuang, J. (2018). A test on methods for MC estimation based on
1324 earthquake catalog. *Earth and Planetary Physics*, 2(2), 150–162.
1325 <https://doi.org/10.26464/epp2018015>

1326 Zlotnicki, J. (2015). Dynamics of volcanic eruptions: Understanding electric signatures for
1327 activity monitoring. *Comptes Rendus Geoscience*, 347(3), 112–123.
1328 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crte.2015.05.003>

1329